

ASSESSING MANUFACTURING EXECUTION SYSTEM CRITICAL FACTORS AND READINESS OF SELECTED SEMICONDUCTOR COMPANIES IN LAGUNA: BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MANAGEMENT INTERVENTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This research explored the current state of readiness among selected semiconductor companies in their start-up implementation of Manufacturing Execution System (MES) and the associated challenges and interventions. The study provided insights into the technological, organizational, and environmental dimensions of MES implementation and proposed management interventions to drive successful integration within semiconductor manufacturing companies. Utilizing a survey-based methodology, the research quantified and analyzed the technological, organizational, and environmental factors influencing the preparedness of these companies for MES implementation. This research refers to the existing body of knowledge by offering a detailed analysis of MES readiness levels, challenges, and management interventions within the semiconductor manufacturing sector. The findings aimed to inform industry practitioners, policymakers, and researchers, providing valuable insights for enhancing the successful integration of MES in semiconductor manufacturing processes, ultimately contributing to improved operational efficiency in the global market. The result of the research using a survey questionnaire, which was distributed to three semiconductor companies having six representatives each, were analyzed to assess the readiness levels of selected semiconductor companies regarding MES implementation using weighted sums. The results provided a quantitative foundation for understanding MES readiness levels among the selected semiconductor companies, offering actionable insights for strategic decision-making.

Keywords: *Manufacturing Execution System, readiness, challenges, management interventions, technological, organizational, environmental.*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid evolution of modern manufacturing has made enhancing productivity a top priority for organizations. To meet customer demands and remain competitive, companies are increasingly turning to technological advancements like Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES). MES software optimizes and controls manufacturing operations, offering real-time visibility, data analysis, and efficient tracking of production actions. By leveraging MES, companies can improve efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance product quality. In today's market, businesses must compete on various performance objectives, necessitating increased coordination and collaboration. Assessing a company's readiness for MES implementation involves evaluating its technological, organizational, and environmental factors. MES adoption is crucial for efficient, agile, and data-driven manufacturing operations, with its implementation tailored to each company's specific needs. Studies on MES impact and readiness assessment help organizations understand the benefits and challenges associated in manufacturing. By exploring the impact of MES, companies can gain insights into operational improvements and strategic implications, paving the way for enhanced competitiveness and success in the manufacturing landscape.

Review of Pertinent Literatures

The literature has emphasized that MES is one of the Industry 4.0 tools since it allows for the planning of technical operations carried out at specific workplaces. However, it is discovered that MES, compared to other "traditional" networks, combines several types of application capabilities into a single system through its varied operational demands. As a result, MES can be described as technologically diversified as it aids in high-tech device manufacturing by controlling complexities, preserving quality, and optimizing production processes (Leng et al., 2020; Sahoo & Lo, 2022). According to the study of Zwolinska et al. (2020), where organizational model of readiness used, the created readiness algorithm's implementation in the MES enabled immediate oversight of the generated variability. For a different system of five machines, the developed solutions were tested.

In accordance with the readiness assessment for MES implementation, studies show that one method of understanding the current state of preparedness prior to deploying a MES system is by evaluating the benefits, drawbacks, opportunities, and hazards connected with a plan like this. As a result, on the other hand, there were still issues and difficulties with the installation of MES that could occasionally cause problems and obstruct the development's success. Furthermore, considering the current context of digital shifts, several modern firms are discovering that their capacity to confront and adapt to change across an organization has developed into a crucial component of survival. Management interventions were presented by a number of literatures that elaborate on this point.

Research Framework

The conceptual framework of the study was developed to understand the different factors on the implementation of MES. The readiness assessment of the research is important and used to analyze the status of the organization's level of readiness in using the MES. The problems or challenges encountered in the implementation of MES were analyzed based on the technological, organizational, and environmental factors. Technological factor refers to the function on the development of an organization's relative advantage and compatibility. Organizational factor refers to the optimization pertaining to the adaptability organizational mode and workflow, traditional thinking mode, and support from management. And lastly, the environmental factor refers to the connectivity of the enterprise levels for perceptions and attitudes in adoption. The identification of the readiness and challenges of the selected semiconductor company were used to develop a management intervention plan in driving MES.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

Research Objectives

This study specifically aimed to target the following objectives:

1. To determine readiness level of the selected semiconductor companies on the start-up implementation of MES.
2. To identify the levels of readiness in confronting the top three problems/challenges encountered on the implementation of (MES) with regards to the following factors:

- a. Technological; and
 - b. Organizational; and
 - c. Environmental
3. To determine the management interventions can be developed for manufacturing companies to enhance the implementation of MES.
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher used descriptive research design in gathering and analyzing the research data. The purpose of the study is to evaluate and determine the readiness of the selected semiconductor company in the implementation of the Manufacturing Execution System and address the problems and challenges encountered. The primary data was gathered through a survey questionnaire that collected quantitative data. In this study, the respondents were from the selected companies in Laguna.

Research Locale

The researcher conducted a study on selected semiconductor companies in Laguna. The identified companies were contacted to agree to participate in the research study. The three participating companies were in the province of Laguna — one company from Cabuyao, one from Calamba, and one from Biñan. The researcher explored one type of manufacturing process. This enhanced the robustness and applicability of the research findings in the three selected semiconductor manufacturing. The organization that participated in the study was from the department associated with the development and execution of MES.

Population and Sampling Design

The researcher purposively selected one representative from the managerial position, two representatives from supervisory position, and three representatives from the operational position from each company to answer the survey questionnaire. This is to ensure that the respondents have enough knowledge about the company's initiative in implementing the manufacturing execution system.

Respondents were selected for their perceived knowledge of manufacturing execution systems process. The survey respondents were represented by their expertise in the implementation of manufacturing execution system.

Research Instruments

The survey questionnaire was used as a research instrument in gathering relevant information from the respondents. The use of a Likert Scale questionnaire as a written instrument was used for quantitative data collection. The five-point Likert scale as interval

like rank level of measurement was used. The survey instrument consisted of three parts. Part I of the survey questionnaire consists of the respondent's personal profile including their name, number of years working in the company, department, and position. For Part II of the questionnaire, the first research question was answered. It is focused on collecting the respondent's information on their organization's readiness level in the implementation of MES. For Part III of the questionnaire, the second research question was addressed. This is focused on determining the challenges/problems encountered on the implementation of MES focused on assessing the three areas of the organization factors (Technological, Environmental, and Organizational).

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sent a letter of request to the selected semiconductor companies to conduct the research study. The researcher sought the participants' permission to participate in the survey and provide a clear and concise explanation of the study. To help the researcher save time and money, the questionnaires were sent to all participating companies' contact persons, which allowed the respondents to answer at their convenient time using Microsoft Forms. The survey questionnaire was retrieved after five working days. The survey questionnaire results were encoded in excel for tabulation. Results were tallied for analysis and interpretation. The results of the data analysis were reported in a clear and concise manner and interpreted to draw meaningful conclusions and insights.

As this study used different levels of measurement to gather data, the respondents were allowed to choose scales in answering the research questions. Likert scale with five-point rating scale was used to gather data on assessing the readiness and problems/challenges encountered of the organization in implementing the MES.

Management and Treatment of Data

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data collected. The researcher used the scaling method to analyze the quantitative data gathered. This interprets the respondent's answers from the questionnaire related to the research questions and objectives. Interpreting neutral results in a Likert scale involves understanding that respondents have chosen a middle-ground option, indicating a lack of strong agreement or disagreement with the statements or questions presented. The neutral response suggests that individuals may not strongly lean toward either a positive or negative sentiment regarding the subject under consideration. Within this, a neutral response provided qualitative data that can complement and contextualize the quantitative Likert scale responses. This helped the researcher uncover the reasons behind the neutral responses and provide a more comprehensive view of participants' perspectives. The survey questionnaire result was evaluated statistically. The data was checked, processed, and ready for analysis after the data was collected. By categorizing the questionnaire in accordance with the topics presented in the research questions and objectives, the researcher analyzed the information gathered from the respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The readiness level of the selected semiconductor companies on the start-up implementation of MES

Table 1. Readiness state of selected semiconductor companies on the implementation of Manufacturing Execution System (MES)

READINESS INDICATOR	Selected Semiconductor Companies Weighted sums / Interpretation		
	A	B	C
RQ_1.1 The organization is ready of the benefits and potential impact of implementing an MES.	21 READY	25 READY	23 READY
RQ_1.2 The organization is ready to conduct a comprehensive analysis of current manufacturing processes and identified areas for improvement.	24 READY	27 FULLY READY	24 READY
RQ_1.3 The roles and responsibilities related to MES implementation are ready to be define within the organization.	24 READY	26 READY	21 READY
RQ_1.4 The project goals, timelines, and milestones for MES implementation are ready.	24 READY	21 READY	21 READY
RQ_1.5 The organization's strategic goals is ready to align with the implementation of an MES.	23 READY	27 FULLY READY	23 READY
RQ_1.6 The organization can communicate the importance and benefits of an MES to employees at all levels.	24 READY	26 READY	25 READY
RQ_1.7 The organization is ready to have necessary hardware infrastructure (servers, workstations, etc.) to support an MES.	22 READY	25 READY	18 SOMEWHAT READY
RQ_1.8 The existing manufacturing machines and equipment are ready of integrating with an MES.	20 SOMEWHAT READY	25 READY	22 READY
RQ_1.9 The organization is ready to assessed and addressed potential resistance to adopting new technologies and changes in work processes.	21 READY	24 READY	23 READY
RQ_1.10 The organization is ready to conduct a skills gap analysis to identify areas where additional training may be required.	22 READY	25 READY	23 READY

RQ_1.11 Employees are ready on learning and embracing new ways of working with the introduction of an MES.	24 READY	25 READY	22 READY
RQ_1.12 The organization is ready for managing potential risks and challenges during the MES implementation process.	21 READY	22 READY	22 READY
LEVEL OF READINESS PER SELECTED SEMICONDUCTOR COMPANIES	270 READY	298 READY	267 READY

The readiness assessment for implementing a Manufacturing Execution System (MES) across three selected semiconductor companies (A, B, and C) reveals a generally positive outlook with a comprehensive overview of their preparedness across various key indicators. The assessment encompasses various aspects of organizational preparedness and is categorized into different criteria. All three companies were found well-prepared for MES implementation, with Company B having the highest readiness score and Company C having the lowest readiness score. As it turns out, they are in a crucial stage where the selected companies find themselves not fully ready but positioned at a ready level. This intermediate status signifies that while progress has been made, there are still notable gaps to address. These gaps may manifest in technological, organizational, and environmental areas that collectively contribute to operational readiness. In summary, while all three semiconductor companies exhibit a general readiness for MES implementation, Company B stands out as the most prepared across various indicators. Company C, while generally ready, may benefit from improvements in hardware infrastructure readiness. The detailed assessment provides insights into specific areas where each company excels and where there is room for improvement.

The levels of readiness in confronting the top three problems/challenges encountered on the implementation of (MES) with regards to the following factors:

a. Technological; and

Table 2. Top three challenges in Technological factor assessment in implementation of Manufacturing Execution System (MES)

RANK	WEIGHTED SUMS	TECHNOLOGICAL FACTOR INDICATOR	AGREEMENT LEVEL
1	59	The organization is compatible of the existing manufacturing machines and equipment with the MES.	Neutral
2	61	The organization has a good network bandwidth, reliability, or security for the MES.	Neutral
	61	The organization is ready for the challenges in integrating the MES with other software systems.	Neutral
3	62	The organization has sufficient technical expertise or support team to manage and maintain the MES.	Neutral

The result of organizational factor assessment indicators identifies the adaptability in the implementation of MES. The technological readiness assessment reveals a generally positive outlook for MES implementation, with strengths in hardware infrastructure and data integrity, though with areas of neutrality in network capabilities and equipment compatibility.

The top three challenges encountered based on the weighted sums were determined on above table, results shows that facing risks is an inherent challenge for any organization involved in change management, and for a manufacturing execution system to be beneficial to each organization, it must undergo significant customization (Yang et al., 2022). Any delays in these activities can adversely affect the effectiveness of the MES, diminishing the value of the insights it provides. It is also crucial to establish safety precautions, including authentication, encryption, authorization, firewalls, and antivirus measures. The real-time insights provided by MES enable timely and well-informed decision-making throughout the entire manufacturing process, from raw material processing to the production of final goods. The implementation of MES can enhance the reliability, productivity, and cost-effectiveness of businesses by monitoring and optimizing manufacturing processes.

b. Organizational; and

Table 3. Top three challenges in Organizational factor assessment in implementation of Manufacturing Execution System (MES)

RANK	WEIGHTED SUMS	ORGANIZATIONAL FACTOR INDICATOR	AGREEMENT LEVEL
1	60	The organization has sufficient communication of the importance and benefits of the MES to employees at all levels.	Neutral
		The organization has sufficient financial resources allocated for the MES implementation project.	Neutral
2	62	The organization has dedicated project team responsible for MES implementation.	Neutral
3	63	The organization has adequate change management efforts in implementing the MES.	Agree
	63	The organization has defined project goals, timelines, and milestones for the MES implementation.	Agree

The organizational readiness assessment exhibits strong organizational readiness, including a clear understanding of MES benefits, thorough process analysis, and proactive change management efforts. Based on the result, Inadequate communication within organizations can lead to misunderstandings, disruptions, and mistakes. Subsequently, when implementing a MES, adjustments to procedures and workflows may be necessary. Careful selection of personnel is imperative, as they play a vital role in the execution of the software process. The success of the entire project might have been jeopardized by a choice of inappropriate team individuals and an ineffective or powerful convey manager. As the organization enters the phase of restructuring its operations, improvements to management are deemed necessary. Lastly, the presence, guidance, and support of management convey to team members that they are informed about and supportive of ongoing developments. This alleviates concerns, reduces anxiety, and instills greater confidence in workers regarding the future. A dedicated, engaged, and cohesive leadership, united in its vision for the organization, serves as the catalyst for change from the top.

c. Environmental;

Table 4. Top three challenges in Environmental factor assessment in implementation of Manufacturing Execution System (MES)

RANK	WEIGHTED SUMS	ENVIRONMENTAL FACTOR INDICATOR	AGREEMENT LEVEL
1	60	The organization is ready for the challenges in ensuring the scalability and upgradability of the technology infrastructure for future MES requirements.	Neutral
2	62	The organization has low complexity and variability in product configurations, making it easy to adapt the MES to different product lines.	Agree
3	63	The organization has good interoperability or compatibility between different MES systems used by suppliers or partners in the industry.	Agree
	63	The organization is ready for the challenges in ensuring the compatibility and integration of the MES with existing technology systems.	Agree

Regarding environmental readiness, the organization demonstrates robustness in standardization, adaptability to market changes, and compliance with regulatory requirements, while scalability considerations present an opportunity for enhancement. Overall, the detailed assessments highlight areas of strength and opportunities for targeted interventions to optimize readiness for successful MES integration.

The effective implementation of MES relies on the accuracy of data. If the data quality is subpar, the system may produce inaccurate or inconsistent results, leading to potential production delays, quality issues, or other complications. Inadequate training poses a significant barrier to the successful adoption of MES. Insufficient training for the new technology may lead production personnel to use it incorrectly, resulting in errors, delays, or compromised quality. Addressing the introduction of new technologies, unexpected opportunities, and shifts in customer interactions within a market are all facets of change management. Integrating MES with other platforms and systems can be a strategic investment for manufacturing businesses. This integration can result in improved customer satisfaction, reduced waste and errors, increased flexibility, and higher revenue, along with enhanced visibility and control over production processes.

The management interventions can be developed for manufacturing companies to enhance the implementation of MES

FACTOR	READINESS ASSESSMENT INDICATOR	MANAGEMENT INTERVENTION	ACTION PLAN	OUTCOME
Technological	The organization is compatible of the existing manufacturing machines and equipment with the MES.	Conduct a comprehensive equipment and software compatibility assessment. Identify machines and equipment that may require updates or modifications to integrate seamlessly with the MES.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invest in necessary upgrades or retrofitting of existing machines to meet MES compatibility requirements. Collaborate with equipment manufacturers or vendors to ensure firmware or software updates for compatibility. 	Improved integration of MES with manufacturing machines, ensuring smooth data exchange and process synchronization.
Technological	The organization has a good network bandwidth, reliability, or security for the MES.	Evaluate and enhance the organization's network infrastructure. Implement security measures and reliability checks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Upgrade network hardware and increase bandwidth to handle the data flow generated by MES. Implement security protocols and measures to safeguard MES data and communication. Establish redundancy and failover mechanisms for network reliability. 	A robust and secure network infrastructure that supports the uninterrupted operation of the MES.
Technological	The organization is ready for the challenges in integrating the MES with other software systems.	Establish an integration task force. Conduct regular reviews and updates to integration processes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage with IT specialists and software developers to create standardized interfaces and protocols for seamless integration. Establish clear communication channels between MES and other software systems to ensure data consistency. Conduct thorough testing and validation during the integration process. 	Successful integration of MES with other software systems, streamlining data flow and improving overall system efficiency.
Technological	The organization has sufficient technical expertise or support team to manage and maintain the MES.	Strengthen the organization's technical expertise and support capabilities to effectively manage and maintain the MES.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess team competencies regularly. Provide ongoing training to address emerging technological needs. 	A competent and well-equipped technical team capable of effectively managing and maintaining the MES, minimizing downtime and disruptions.

FACTOR	READINESS ASSESSMENT INDICATOR	MANAGEMENT INTERVENTION	ACTION PLAN	OUTCOME
(...Continue)	The organization has sufficient communication of the importance and benefits of the MES to employees at all levels.	Implement targeted communication strategies. Conduct feedback sessions to understand employee perceptions and address concerns.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct awareness sessions, workshops, and training programs to educate employees about how MES will positively impact their work and the overall efficiency of the organization. • Provide regular updates through internal communication channels, emphasizing the strategic significance of MES in achieving organizational goals. 	Improved employee understanding and support for MES implementation, fostering a positive attitude towards the upcoming changes.
Organizational	The organization has dedicated project team responsible for MES implementation.	Ensure team members have clear roles and responsibilities. Facilitate regular team meetings to enhance collaboration and coordination.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Form a cross-functional project team comprising members from IT, operations, and relevant departments. • Clearly define roles and responsibilities within the project team. 	A well-coordinated and focused project team capable of driving the MES implementation forward efficiently.
	The organization has adequate change management efforts in implementing the MES.	Conduct regular change management training for employees. Establish a feedback loop to address concerns and adapt change management strategies as needed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct change impact assessments to identify potential challenges and areas of resistance. • Establish a communication plan to keep employees informed about changes and address concerns. • Provide training programs to help employees adapt to new processes and technologies. 	Minimized resistance, increased employee buy-in, and a smoother transition to MES implementation.
	The organization has defined project goals, timelines, and milestones for the MES implementation.	Regularly review and update project goals. Conduct milestone celebrations to boost team morale and motivation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a detailed project plan outlining timelines for each phase of implementation. • Define key milestones and regularly assess progress against these milestones. 	Improved project management, ensuring that the MES implementation stays on track, is completed on time, and meets the established goals.

FACTOR	READINESS ASSESSMENT INDICATOR	MANAGEMENT INTERVENTION	ACTION PLAN	OUTCOME
Environmental	(...Continue)			
	The organization is ready for the challenges in ensuring the scalability and upgradability of the technology infrastructure for future MES requirements.	Conduct a comprehensive review of current technology infrastructure. Develop a plan to enhance scalability and upgradability based on future MES requirements. Seek input from IT experts and stakeholders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invest in scalable hardware and software solutions that can accommodate the expected growth in data and processing demands. Establish a regular review and upgrade cycle for technology components to stay ahead of MES advancements. 	A technology infrastructure that can seamlessly scale to meet the evolving needs of the MES without significant disruptions.
	The organization has low complexity and variability in product configurations, making it easy to adapt the MES to different product lines.	Continuously monitor product configurations and streamline processes to maintain adaptability. Implement a regular review process for product complexity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop standardized processes and workflows within the MES to accommodate variations in product configurations efficiently. Implement modular and flexible MES configurations that can easily adapt to changes in product specifications. Provide training programs to employees to ensure they understand and can easily navigate MES adjustments for different product lines. 	Efficient and streamlined MES adaptation to various product configurations, reducing complexity and minimizing disruptions.
	The organization has good interoperability or compatibility between different MES systems used by suppliers or partners in the industry.	Maintain regular communication with suppliers and partners. Conduct joint assessments to address any emerging interoperability challenges.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish communication channels with suppliers and partners to understand their MES specifications and requirements. Collaborate with suppliers and partners to implement standardized interfaces and data exchange protocols. 	Improved integration and seamless data exchange between the organization's MES and those of its suppliers or partners, enhancing overall supply chain efficiency.
	The organization is ready for the challenges in ensuring the compatibility and integration of the MES with existing technology systems.	Implement regular system integration checks and updates. Foster collaboration between IT and MES implementation teams to address integration challenges promptly.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct a thorough assessment of existing systems to identify potential integration challenges. Collaborate with IT teams to ensure that MES implementation aligns with existing technology architecture. 	Successful integration of MES with existing technology systems, minimizing disruptions and optimizing overall system performance.

In the technological domain, enhancements in MES integration with manufacturing machines, network infrastructure security, integration with other software systems, and technical team competence are recommended. These improvements aim to ensure smooth data exchange, uninterrupted system operation, streamlined processes, and effective maintenance, respectively. Organizational improvements involve boosting employee understanding and support, establishing clear project roles, minimizing resistance through change management training, and enhancing project management

practices. Environmental recommendations include ensuring technology scalability, streamlining MES adaptation to product configurations, improving integration with suppliers/partners, and optimizing integration with existing systems to minimize disruptions and enhance overall performance. These recommendations collectively aim to optimize readiness and facilitate successful MES implementation.

Conclusions

The study concludes that there is a high readiness level among the selected semiconductor companies for MES implementation. Technological aspect, there's a generally positive state of readiness, but improvements are needed in network aspects, compatibility assessments, and ongoing skill enhancement for the technical team. Organizational factors suggest a need for better communication strategies, project team optimization, and financial planning. Environmental factors highlight the importance of ongoing scalability assessments, technology infrastructure enhancements, and staying updated on regulatory standards. Management interventions should focus on implementing proactive measures based on action plans for each indicator, strengthening communication strategies, optimizing project teams, conducting comprehensive financial reviews, and ensuring ongoing compliance with regulatory standards. Regular reviews and updates are essential to align with evolving technological requirements and industry advancements.

Recommendations

Future research in Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES) should prioritize several key areas to deepen our understanding and contribute to MES development. Firstly, exploring the intersection of MES and sustainable manufacturing practices is crucial, investigating how MES can optimize resources, reduce waste, and foster environmentally friendly production processes, while assessing its impact on economic and environmental sustainability within manufacturing operations. Secondly, emphasis should be placed on understanding the dynamics of human-machine collaboration within MES environments. This involves designing MES interfaces to facilitate smooth interaction between human operators and automated systems and exploring the role of training programs and skill development in enhancing productivity through human-machine collaboration. Lastly, conducting cross-industry comparative analyses of MES implementations is recommended to compare challenges, successes, and best practices across diverse sectors like automotive, pharmaceuticals, and electronics manufacturing. Utilizing alternative research methodologies such as qualitative or mixed methods research, including in-depth interviews, can offer more comprehensive insights into MES adoption and performance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher had written consent on the selected participants of the study. Participants were provided with clear and understandable information about the study's

purpose, procedures, benefits, and their rights to voluntary participation. The researcher ensured the confidentiality and anonymity of the participants data. The participants' privacy was respected, and the data collected was stored securely and only accessible by the researcher. The data was used solely for research purposes and reported in aggregate form to maintain participant confidentiality.

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